

REVIEW ARTICLE

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Second and Third Generation Biofuel Sources: A Comparative Review of Benefits, Challenges, and Conversion Technologies

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Abstract

Background: Second and third-generation biofuels have been thoroughly researched as sustainable and renewable alternatives to fossil fuels, although their large-scale deployment is limited by techno-economic and environmental concerns and inconsistent assessments in different studies. Recent advancements call for a critical review and investigation of the field. **Objectives:** This review aims to compare the second and third generation feedstocks for biofuel conversion technologies, their techno-economic feasibility, environmental performance and trade-offs in the related processes. **Methods:** We used 36 open-access papers that were published recently (2020-2025) from various databases to focus on our objective for this paper review. An analysis of papers was done to gather useful information for comparative analysis. **Findings:** The analysis revealed that 2nd generation biofuels are constrained by pretreatment severity and enzymatic hydrolysis costs, whereas 3rd generation systems are plagued by energy intensive cultivation, harvesting and dewatering. Although microalgae exhibit higher productivity than lignocellulosic feedstocks, their net energy balance and production costs make it unfavourable, without co-product valorization and renewable energy use. Life-cycle assessments also demonstrate variable environmental benefits related to site conditions and environmental burden shifting. **Significance:** Unlike previous reviews that focus on a feedstock yield or a conversion technique and its efficiency, this review integrates techno-economic analysis and environmental aspects across different generations, identifying the limitations that exist, and proposes an economically feasible and environmentally safe biofuel development pathway.

Keywords: Second Generation Biofuel; Third Generation Biofuel; Biofuel Feedstocks; Biofuel Conversion Technologies; Life-cycle assessment; Techno-economic analysis

1 Introduction

The transition towards sustainable energy has increased global interest in biofuels as renewable alternatives to fossil fuels. Early (first) generation biofuels were mainly derived from food-based feedstocks. This raised concerns regarding food security, land-use competition with fertile land and environmental stability. Due to this, research has shifted to the 2nd generation (lignocellulosic biomass) and 3rd generation (algal) biofuels, which offer greater resource efficiency and reduced competition with food systems.

Over the past decade, a lot of advancements have been seen in biomass pretreatment, enzymatic hydrolysis, fermentation strategies, algal cultivation, processing technologies, etc. Simultaneous and combined developments in Techno-economic analysis and Life Cycle assessments have enhanced understanding of the economic and environmental effects of the related biofuel production pathways. However, despite these advancements, 2nd and 3rd generation biofuels remain to be deployed at a large scale commercially.

Many research articles examine specific feedstock classification, conversion technology, sustainability metrics and emphasize biomass yield optimization or conversion efficiency; and treat techno-economic and environmental aspects separately. Also, recent developments like integrated biorefineries, energy-normalized performance metrics and renewable energy integration are not consistently synthesized.

1.1 Research Contributions

This review makes the following contributions:

1. Provides a comparative techno-economic assessment of 2nd and 3rd generation biofuel pathways based of dominant cost contributors rather than yield metrics alone.
2. Integrates environmental life-cycle assessments to greenhouse gas mitigation, energy source sensitivity and environmental burden shifting.
3. Uses recent advancements to propose system-level strategies to improve sustainability and scalability of 2nd and 3rd generation biofuels.

1.2 Research Gaps

Although extensive research in the area has been done, critical gaps remain in understanding how techno-economic and environmental limitations are related and dependent across the biofuel generations. Also, existing review insufficiently address energy-normalized performance indicators, co-product valorization strategies and the varying nature of environmental benefits and concerns over different systems and energy sources.

1.3 Research Questions

This review addresses the following questions:

- What techno-economic factors most strongly limit 2nd and 3rd generation biofuel deployment?
- How do environmental impacts vary with feedstock type, conversion technology and energy inputs?
- Which strategies offer the most promising pathways for sustainable and feasible biofuel scale-up?

2 Review Methodology

Published articles for this review were found using the databases ScienceDirect, MDPI, BMC, ResearchGate, Frontiers, Nature & SpringerOpen. The keywords used were “Biofuel energy crops”, “Biomass”, “Feedstocks”, “Conversion Techniques”, “Second Generation”, “Third Generation”, “Sorghum”, “Jatropha”, “Miscanthus”, “Switchgrass”, “Bioenergy Crops”, “Microalgae”, “Algae”, etc. Only papers published from 2020 to 2025 were accepted. Non-English papers were rejected. Each paper’s abstracts and conclusions were read to decide the paper’s relevance to the chosen topic. Only open-access papers were used.

3 Overview

3.1 Second Generation Feedstock

3.1.1. Sorghum

Sorghum is a drought resistant bioenergy crop, which means it requires less water and fertilizer to grow, produces minimal greenhouse gas emissions and has high photosynthetic efficiency⁽¹⁾. Due to these parameters, it easily grows in marginal lands, therefore offering no competition to food. Sorghum juice obtained by stem pressing is fermented and distilled for bioethanol production, and the remaining waste like sorghum bagasse and leaves can be used as a feedstock for pyrolysis⁽²⁾. In Chad, the evaluation of 137 specific species has been found showing great potential with respect to yield amount⁽³⁾. Research and scientific advancements regarding the genetic traits of sorghum are maximising yield and drought resistance, while also targeting biomass recalcitrance reduction, placing sorghum as one of the best second-generation biofuel crops⁽⁴⁾.

As seen in Table 1, hydrothermal and alkaline pretreatment-based pathways dominate sorghum bioethanol studies. However, pretreatment severity results in an increase in sugar release but also in electricity consumption, showing a yield-cost paradox. Saccharification efficiency is enhanced by strategies using microbial co-culturing. Also, integrated approaches to have fermentation with waste valorisation improves efficiency at the cost of complexity and expenses.

Table 1. Comparison of different studies processing Sorghum.

Feedstock	Conversion Method	End Prod- uct	Yield/ Output	Limitation	Ref- er- ence
Sweet sorghum juice/ bagasse	Hydrothermal pretreatment + Pre-hydrolysis and Simultaneous Saccharification and Fermentation (PSSF)	Bioethanol	22.17g/L ethanol, 2.46 MJ/g biomass energy input	High electricity demand - 79% of total input.	(5)
Sweet sorghum residue	NaOH pretreatment + Separate Hydrolysis and Fermentation (SHF) via microbial culturing	Bioethanol	16.8 g/L ethanol	High enzyme demand and its strict control in process.	(6)
Sweet sorghum biomass residues	Fermentation + Pyrolysis	Bioethanol + Bio oil	Multi- product output	Complex integrated process	(2)
Sweet sorghum (Chadian accessions)	Direct Juice fermentation	Bioethanol	Genotype dependent - 322 to 1194 L/ha	Yield Variability (Climate and Genotype)	(3)
Sweet sorghum genotypes	Juice fermentation + Lignocellulosic bagasse conversion	Bioethanol	Highly variable yield depending on species - 2127 to 13486 L/ha	Yield Variability	(1)

3.1.2. Jatropha

Jatropha is a very resilient and drought-tolerant crop that is able to adapt to growth in marginal lands with tropical and subtropical temperatures and needs a relatively lesser amount of water and fertilizer⁽⁷⁾. Jatropha plant also grows very quickly, can undergo reproduction very easily and produces high quality oil with high triglyceride concentration which can be processed at lower costs compared to other feedstocks, making it an amazing source of biodiesel^{(7), (8)}. This is reinforced by the high cetane no. of 55.43 recorded in a study⁽⁹⁾. Jatropha can be grown in land that is degraded to restore its respective ecosystem's quality and structure⁽⁷⁾. It also has reduced carbon monoxide (14-30%) and particulate matter emissions (11-15%). Also, with less modifications, a diesel engine easily runs on Jatropha-based biodiesel⁽¹⁰⁾. Research to integrate jatropha biofuel as a jet biofuel due to its great potential is still ongoing.⁽¹¹⁾

As seen from the comparison Table 2 of all studies of Jatropha, we see that the seeds and fruit husks contribute are processed to give liquid fuels and gaseous ones respectively. One common problem is the high FFA (Free Fatty Acid) content, which requires pre-treatment and use of enzymes to avoid soap formation. There also is a trade-off between yield and process efficiency.

Table 2. Comparison of different studies processing *Jatropha curcasto* give end product of Biodiesel/ Jatropha Oil.

Conversion Method	Yield	Limitation	Ref-er-ence
Microwave/ Ultrasonic pretreatment + Mechanical Extraction	25.1% oil yield+ 5.03% (microwave) +6.75% (ultrasonic)	High energy consumption for production - 2052.5 W.h/kg oil.	(10)
Lipid Extraction/ Transesterification	35-40% (seed) and 50-60% (kernel)	Process complexity, catalyst efficiency and cost.	(8)
Transesterification	30-40% (seed)	High FFA content and oil viscosity.	(7)
Enzymatic Transesterification/ pyrolysis	30-60%	3% more CO2 generated than diesel	(9)
Gasifica-tion/Transesterification and Lipid Extraction	75% of fruit weight into syngas (theoretical potential), 35- 40% (seed, 1892 L/ha/year)	Limited implementation of gasification process for biofuel production.High FFA content affecting transesterification efficiency	(11)

3.1.3. Rice Husk

Rice hulls or husks, are globally one of the most abundant agricultural wastes and make up 20% of the entire harvested weight of rice. As a result 776.4 million tons of rice production produced 155 million tons of rice husk, treated as a waste. Usually, this waste is composted, burned openly or disposed improperly. Open burning leads to the introduction of particulate matter and greenhouse gases and due to its high silica concentration, it decreases soil fertility. Due to it being the waste of a food crop, it does not take up any land for the sole reason of getting biomass. It also has a high average Energy Sustainability Index (ESI) of 0.62 which reflects its superiority as an environmentally and economically friendly feedstock. Different conversion processes of Rice Husk is presented (Table 3).

Table 3. Tabulation of different conversion processes of Rice Husk and their importance from⁽¹²⁾.

Conversion Process	End Product	Performance Metric and data
Saccharification and Fermentation	Bioethanol	250 L/t of of dry fee with alkali pretreatment, up to 85.4% conversion rate depending on yeast species and treatment
Transesterification	Biodiesel	Operating Temp of 60-70 deg. C, shorter reaction times relative to other feedstocks due to high surface area
Catalyst Formation	Solid Catalyst	Same performance as commercial alkyl catalysts and cheaper.
Gasification	Syngas	High carbon content which leads high power generation, used in applications related to power generation, drying and cooking
Pelletization	Solid Fuel	High density (Pellet/ Briquettes), is a perfect substitution for coal and diesel in industrial boilers.

3.1.4. Miscanthus and Switchgrass

Miscanthus and switchgrass are highly resource efficient 2nd generation biofuel crops that grows in marginal and heavy metal polluted lands. This means it offers no obstruction to food crops and has a low indirect land use change. However they differ in their downstreaming process as miscanthus is a metal-excluder that takes heavy metals into its root system but not into its aerial parts, whereas switchgrass is a phytoextractor that takes heavy metals fully into its leaves and stem. This implies, switchgrass is better at removing metals from the soil but is worse to downstream to get proper biofuel⁽¹³⁾. Biomass yields of miscanthus and switchgrass peak in the 7th and 6th years respectively, provided nitrogen levels are properly maintained to avoid diminishing returns⁽¹⁴⁾. Humic acid and Mycorrhizae (HAM) significantly improves relevant harvestable yields in degraded soils by using beneficial soil microbes⁽¹³⁾. Switchgrass shows massive carbohydrate content which results in low requirement of feedstock per megajoule of energy generated, while both emit very less carbon dioxide and sequester it easily and have superior carbon efficiency⁽¹⁵⁾. However, they require high water input and consume a lot of energy for biomass handling and

maintenance of plants⁽¹⁶⁾. Research is being done to reduce severity of pretreatments to breakdown lignocellulose by exploring genetic engineering⁽¹⁷⁾.

Table 4. Comparison of different studies processing Miscanthus and Switchgrass.

Pretreatment	Conversion Method	End Product	Yield	Limitation	Reference
Enzymatic Processing	Enzymatic hydrolysis and Fermentation	Bioethanol	4,400 - 5,600 L/ha (Miscanthus), 370-450 gallons/acre (Switchgrass)	High process cost and advanced processing technologies needed for lignocellulose breakdown	(17)
Drying	Gasification / Fast Pyrolysis	Syngas / Bio-oil	Average conversion yield of 21% wt	High cost. Drying is required to minimize energy losses during heating	(17)
Dilute Acid	Separated Saccharification & Co-fermentation	Bioethanol	Dry Biomass and Energy efficiencies of 0.36 L/kg, 46.2 and 0.34 L/kg, 39.8% for switchgrass and miscanthus respectively	Needs high water input and treatment and generates notable CO2 emissions.	(15)
Steam Explosion and Alkali	Enzymatic saccharification	Fermentable sugars (Miscanthus)	Near 100% Saccharification yield	Drop in yield in hexose when alkali is used as catalyst relative to acid.	(18)
Alkali+ Surfactant (Tween 20)	Enzymatic saccharification	Fermentable sugars (Switchgrass)	92% Enzymatic glucan conversion	Needs specific surfactant to block enzymes from binding to leftover lignin.	(18)
Green Liquor (31% Total Titratable Alkali, 166 deg C	Enzymatic Saccharification & Fermentation	Bioethanol (Miscanthus)	171 g/kg of biomass	High salt concentrations leading to additional downsteaming processes	(19)
Acid+ Ionic Liquid	Enzymatic Saccharification & Fermentation	Bioethanol (Miscanthus)	220 g/kg of biomass	Ionic liquids are highly effective but they are costly and hard to manage at large scales.	(19)
Alkaline Twin-Screw Extrusion	Physio-chemical (Extrusion + Alkali)	Fermentable Sugars (Miscanthus)	Cellulose increased to 58.9%, lignin reduced to 12.6%	Produces a black liquor which needs recycling in closed loop	(20)
Semi-Continuous Steam Explosion	Steam Explosion	Cellulosic Biomass (Switchgrass)	Maximized exposed cellulose content	Needs high energy spikes to periodically build and release the pressure in the reactor.	(20)
AFEX+ Water pre-soaking	Physio-chemical	Fermentable Sugars (Miscanthus)	76% Glucose recovery	Needs high pressure reactors and proper handling of volatile ammonia	(20)
Acetic Acid	Fermentation	Biobutanol (Switchgrass)	8.6 g/L Biobutanol	Needs high acidic medium and thermal inputs	(16)
Microwave	Physical Pretreatment	Solubilized Biomass (Miscanthus and Switchgrass)	7% to 10% solubility (liquidification of biomass for further treatment)	High Power Consumption	(16)

As seen from Table 4, hybrid alkaline treatments outperform those with dilute acid by removing lignin and keeping the rest of the cellulose constituents, helping in achieving almost maximum possible yields. Sugar recovery from biomass is achieved without extreme temperatures using surfactants and ionic liquids. However, maximum yields are only achievable for now, using a lot of water and emission of hazardous substances. Viability of these processes depend on recycling catalysts and water.

3.1.5. Wheat Straw (Table 5)

Wheat Straw consists of cellulose, hemicellulose, and lignin. It is widely available at a low cost, which makes it a good second-generation biofuel feedstock^{(18), (20)}. It has higher silica content compared to corn stover, making it harder to hydrolyze than rice straw. On the contrary, it has lower lignin than woody biomass, making it easier to delignify than wood⁽²⁰⁾. It is a well-studied lignocellulosic residue; hence it can be used as a benchmark feedstock for pretreatment severity and conversion efficiency. Its high cellulose and hemicellulose content makes it highly responsive to the chemical pretreatments above^{(15), (18)}. Many studies show pretreatment severity to play a critical role in increasing yield whilst decreasing inhibitor formation. Alkaline pretreatment is used in Wheat Straw to improve enzymatic accessibility for carbohydrates, if done in an optimal amount. Over severe acid pretreatment may lead to more degradation of products and higher energy penalties⁽²⁰⁾. It causes slugging and bed agglomeration in gasification, hence having the requirement for pre-washing and co-feeding strategies. The conversion technique involves pyrolysis and gasification. Pyrolysis for conversion of biomass into char and volatiles. Gasification of char produces syngas. This is helpful in decreasing tar formation and managing ash related issues.⁽²⁰⁾

Table 5. Comparison of different studies processing Wheat straw

Conversion Technique	End Product	Yield/Observation	Limitation	Reference
Dil. Acid pretreatment & fermentation	Bioethanol	200-300 L/ha	Fermentation inhibitors	(20)
Alkaline pretreatment & fermentation	Bioethanol	70-85% cellulose to glucose conversion	High chemical recovery cost	(18), (20)
Enzymatic Hydrolysis	Fermentable sugar	60-80% post pretreatment	High enzyme loading requirement	(20), (21)
Fast pyrolysis	Bio-oil	55-65%	Bio-oil instability Needs upgrading	(22), (23)
Integrated pyrolysis-gasification	Syngas + Heat	93%, giving ethanol yield 39.6%	Complex system	(20)
Combined biorefinery approach	Ethanol + Biogas + Heat	>=80% system efficiency	Capital intensive integration	(2), (21)

3.2 Third Generation Feedstock

Algae feedstocks include micro and macro-algae, classified on the basis of their size and structure (Table 6). Macroalgae are further classified into brown, red and green seaweeds. Microalgae are classified into diatoms, golden algae, green algae and cyanobacteria⁽²⁴⁾. This feedstock overcomes challenges faced by the 2nd generation due to their fast growth rate, strong photosynthetic ability, no competition of land use between food crops and contains lipids and carbohydrates which are more suitable for biofuel generation⁽²⁵⁾. Macroalgae and microalgae also have higher CO2 sequestration efficiencies, can remove harmful pollutants in the environment to help its own growth which also makes it a cost-effective method for water treatment⁽²²⁾. The main constituents of algae biomass and their uses are -

1. Lipids- Mainly triacylglycerols which are suitable for biodiesel production.
2. Carbohydrates- Present in forms of starch and cellulose which is useful in biogas, biohydrogen and bioethanol production. It also can be used to produce chemicals and polymers.
3. Proteins- Used in the food and medical industry.
4. Pigments- Used in the food, cosmetic and medical industry.

Macroalgae can be cultivated using offshore, onshore and integrated culturing, where onshore directly relies on the nutrients and other components from the ocean. Alternatively, onshore methods are controlled and lead to higher quality biomass yield⁽²⁴⁾. Microalgae also are cultivated using 3 systems. Open pond systems consist of artificial, shallow pools with equipment to mix the medium. They are easy to maintain, operate and are cost-efficient which make them a popular choice, but can get contaminated and affected by environmental conditions due to which their biomass productivity and lipid content is relatively less. Photobioreactors are a closed loop system where the environment and parameters that affect the growth of algae can be controlled therefore a higher production rate and quality is achieved^{(26), (27)}. However, due to high initial costs and operations costs, it is not preferred. Hybrid systems resolve the issues of the 2 previous methods and combine their benefits. Phototrophic

systems are those in which the energy source is sunlight. Heterotrophic systems have their energy sources as carbon rich compounds, bio sugars and waste products.

For Macroalgae, lipid creation and algae growth are controlled by light, temperature, pH and CO₂. Higher light levels lead to more growth and enable photosynthesis, high CO₂ levels and a neutral or slightly acidic pH encourage lipid creation but hinder algae growth and vice-versa. Lipids only are produced at specific temperatures. In Microalgae, proper cell growth occurs between pH 8.2-8.7 which is usually attained by addition of CO₂. Blue and red radiations for an illumination period of 16-18 hours with 5-10% intensity and temperatures below 35 deg. C also encourages cell growth⁽²⁶⁾. Nitrogen starvation in the 2nd stage and lower saline levels of the medium optimizes carbohydrate and lipid production^{(22), (28)}. Introduction of mild electrical fields across microalgae can enhance their photosynthetic ability and metabolism, which in turn increases their intake of nutrients and inorganic carbon from the medium⁽²⁹⁾.

One can acquire macroalgae biomass by directly harvesting from the ocean, collected from the shore or from artificial algal growth facilities. Application of electric fields into harvesting systems can also increase biomass yield, reduce the accumulation of biomass in undesirable areas and improve separation efficiency⁽²⁹⁾.

As seen from Table 6, Microalgae are mostly used to produce biodiesel which is done via lipid extraction and transesterification, where the species *Tetraselmis suecica* is a very promising biofuel feedstock. However, the related high energy input and expensive catalyst requirements are huge concerns. Macroalgae processed via Hydrothermal liquefaction achieves bio-yields of 45%. It is able to process wet biomass, but has high operational costs and energy demands. Gasification and pyrolysis are very promising but again have high energy requirements and low conversion efficiency. Depending on the end product, we either would choose micro or macroalgae although more development is needed for their large-scale use.

Lipid extraction processes generate residual biomass rich in protein and carbohydrates. Anaerobic digestion helps in biogas production, energy recovery and nutrient recycling. The net energy output is increased by reducing waste streams.

Table 6. Comparison of different studies processing Micro and Macro Algae

Feedstock	Conversion Method	End Product	Yield	Limitation	Reference
Microalgae (Tetraselmis suecica)	Lipid Extraction, Transesterification	Biodiesel	Energy content 22.2 MJ/kg, Productivity 66 t/ha/yr.	High energy input for extraction, catalyst requirements	(24)
Microalgae (various species)	Lipid Extraction, Pyrolysis, Gasification	Biodiesel, Bio-oil, Syngas	Pyrolysis bio-oil yield 30–50%	High energy consumption and low yield for pyrolysis	(26)
Macroalgae (Brown seaweed)	Hydrothermal Liquefaction	Bio-oil	Hydrothermal liquefaction bio-oil yield 45%	High operational cost for HTL	(24)
Macroalgae (Seaweed)	Hydrothermal Liquefaction	Bio-oil	HTL bio-oil yield: 50–55%	Requires substantial energy and costs for biofuel refinement	(17)

3.3 Conversion Technology for 2nd and 3rd Generation Biomass-

The different conversion technologies used for the conversion of algae and lignocellulosic biomass into biofuels are classified into 3 types based on final product and biomass suitability – chemical, thermochemical and biochemical processes⁽²⁴⁾. Microalgae usually has high lipid content which makes it suitable for biodiesel production, whereas macroalgae contains high carbohydrate and low lipid content which makes it suitable for bioethanol production⁽²⁴⁾. Lignocellulosic biomass contains lignin and crystallized structure of cellulose which need pretreatment methods and cannot undergo techniques that may otherwise be viable for 3rd generation feedstocks⁽²⁰⁾.

Microalgae biomass can be converted using three techniques, Chemical, Thermochemical, and Biochemical (Table 7). Thermochemical techniques like gasification, pyrolysis, and hydrothermal methods. The best way to produce biodiesel is via Lipid Extraction. Four reasons being:

1. Lipid is the source for Biodiesel
2. The thermochemical way will disrupt lipid structure.
3. Fermentation does not work on lipids.
4. This does not produce any unnecessary compounds.⁽²⁷⁾

Severity Factor is generally used for thermochemical pretreatments which combine temperature and residence time. Lower severities led to incomplete biomass deconstruction, whereas higher severities caused sugar degradation and inhibitor formation⁽²⁰⁾.

Table 7. Comparing different pretreatment methods and usability outcomes

Pretreatment	Temperature (°C)	Time (min)	Severity Regime (log R0)	Typical Outcome	Reference
Steam explosion	160-220	1-10	Moderate-High (3-4.5)	High digestibility by enzyme, inhibitor risk	(20)
Hydrothermal	160-200	10-60	Moderate-High (3-4.8)	Good hemicellulose recovery	(20)
Acid treatment	120-190	5-60	Low-Moderate (2.5-4.0)	Selective Hemicellulose removal	(20)

Impact of pretreatment severity and associated energy penalties

The concept of severity uses specific feedstock composition, compared to reaching maximum output. This signifies pretreatment optimization as a multivariable design problem with the end goal of process efficiency per unit of energy and chemical input^{(19), (20)}.

3.3.1. Chemical conversion pathway- Lipid Extraction and Transesterification

Lipid Extraction is carried out with the help of various methods like mechanical cell disruption which are simple but use a lot of energy, solvent extraction which uses chemical solvents for high fuel yield and supercritical fluid techniques which uses supercritical-state CO2 which prevents the need to use solvents but needs good pretreatment for high quality yield. After lipid extraction, the process of converting this yield into biodiesel which is transesterification comes into play. Transesterification involves the conversion of the lipids into fatty acid methyl esters, which is nothing but biodiesel. Non-catalytic processes require methanol and ethanol, but higher yields can be achieved by the application of catalysts. Catalysis using bases increase the speed of the reaction but is less tolerant to free fatty acid. Acid catalysts are more tolerant but need high temperatures, are slower and cause corrosion of equipment used. Enzymatic processes can be carried out easily but are relatively expensive and slow down due to contamination. Transesterification of lignocellulosic biomass is done after delignification, saccharification, and fermentation to increase lipid synthesis^{(8), (11), (23), (24), (30)}.

As seen in Table 8, lipid-based biofuel production uses mechanical/solvent extraction with Alkali catalyzed transesterification for Jatropha and microalgae. Alkali catalysis is the most efficient taking reaction rate and yield into consideration but is sensitive to free fatty acid content which necessitates acid catalysis or pretreatment of feedstock. Supercritical CO2 extraction is a solvent free and high lipid recovery method but has high capital and operation costs. Heterogeneous catalysts have the advantage or reusability but lack stability. Hence, these methods are very dependable, but energy demands, catalyst tolerance, process and economic optimization are needed for large scale use.

Table 8. Comparison of different studies using Lipid extraction and Transesterification techniques

Feedstock	Lipid Extraction	Transesterification	End Product	Yield/ Observation	Limitation	Reference
Jatropha curcas seeds	Mechanical + Solvent extraction	Alkali-catalyzed	Biodiesel	Oil content – 35-40%	Sensitivity to high Free fatty acid content	(11)
Waste cooking oil	Solvent extraction	Acid+ Base Catalyzed	Biodiesel	High conversion despite high free fatty acids	Corrosion, purification needed	(31)
Microalgae	Solvent extraction	Alkali-catalyzed	Biodiesel	High lipid recovery	Drying and solvent energy	(24)
Microalgae	Supercritical CO2	Alkali-catalyzed	Biodiesel	Solvent-free extraction	High capital cost	(8)
Microalgae	Solvent extraction	Heterogeneous-catalyzed	Biodiesel	Catalyst reusable	Catalyst deactivation	(7), (8)
Algae and lipid biomass	Mechanical + solvent extraction + Super critical CO2	Alkali + Base + Enzymatic-catalyzed	Biodiesel	Comparative performance	Scale-up economics	(22), (32)

3.3.2. Thermochemical conversion pathway

3.3.2.1. Pyrolysis & Gasification. Pyrolysis is a process where heat is used to break chemical bonds. Based on the differences in parameters in which the process is carried out, it can be classified into different types. Slow pyrolysis- Heating of biomass between 300-500 deg. Cover a long period of time, yielding biochar, bio-oil and syngas which is a mixture of H₂, CO, CO₂ and CH₄. Fast Pyrolysis- Biomass mixture is rapidly heated at higher temperatures anaerobically for less time and gives a greater yield of bio-oil. Flash Pyrolysis- Here, the mixture is heated at a temperature and timeframe between slow and fast pyrolysis. This method is used to get a good bio-oil yield of a greater quality than that of fast pyrolysis therefore reducing processing costs. Microwave Pyrolysis- Electromagnetic radiation is used to quickly and uniformly heat up the mixture being energy efficient, higher yield quality and more controlled. Catalytic Pyrolysis- It is primarily used to produce high value chemicals and good yield and quality of desired biofuel as well although requires the same number of catalysts as biomass. Gasification is a process where steam is introduced to the biomass being treated at specific parameters like high temperatures and partial oxidation. This produces gaseous biofuels like syngas and fuel gas. It is suited for third generation feedstock with lower lipid content therefore high carbohydrate content ^{(8), (26), (33)}.

Pyrolysis of Lignocellulosic biomass when conducted under fast condition gives high bio-oil yields being roughly 60 to 70% of the feedstock. Catalytic pyrolysis using zeolites are able to reduce instability and increase heating value of the resulting bio-oil, therefore increasing its quality which it does by deoxygenation. Pyrolysis of Rice husk showed a 45% bio-oil yield which is very promising energy production scalability. Sorghum bagasse under gasification process, shows great promise for bio-ethanol production due to greater cold gas efficiency. Liquid biofuels like methanol, Fischer-Tropsch diesel and dimethyl ether can be processed from syngas and generation of heat and power on syngas combustion show great potential in the energy production sector ^{(1), (2), (8), (12), (26), (33)}.

Table 9. Key pyrolysis used in thermochemical biomass conversion

Pyrolysis technique	When to use	Reference
Slow pyrolysis	Bio-char systems with low fuel consumption	(26)
Fast pyrolysis	High bio-oil yield for liquid fuel production	(26)
Flash pyrolysis	Rapid bio-oil production with minimal char formation	(26)

Table 10. Gasification route used in thermochemical biomass conversion

Gasification technique	When to use	Reference
Air gasification	Low-cost syngas for heat and power generation	(26)
Oxygen gasification	High calorific syngas for fuel synthesis	(26)
Steam gasification	Hydrogen rich syngas for advanced biofuels	(33)

Table 9 and 10 present the summary of key pyrolysis and gasification routes used in thermochemical biomass conversion

3.3.2.2. Hydrothermal Liquefaction. This process involves the heating of the mixture to 200-380 deg. C at 5-28 MPa. It is done directly on the wet algae biomass, where the water breaks the biomass down into oils. It can be used for both macro and microalgae ^{(8), (34)}. It is a very promising process for wet algae biomass conversion since it bypasses the energy-intensive processes needed for drying while using moderate temperatures and pressures. However, upgrading of biofuel is a must to remove its unwanted constituents like nitrogen and oxygen ^{(24), (35)}.

As seen in Table 11, Hydrothermal Liquefaction (HTL) is useful for converting wet biomass into energy dense fuel. Using lignocellulosic or algal biomass, we see HTL tolerates high moisture feedstocks and achieves favorable fuel with low economics. By omitting the drying process, we get a higher energy return. However, high pressure needs, fuel upgrading complexity and catalytic costs and durability in reactors are limitations that need to be addressed. Although, we see that the performance of HTL itself mainly depends on reactor design and upgradation needs rather than the feedstock itself. Hence, it is a great conversion pathway for 2nd and 3rd gen feedstocks but needs good infrastructure.

3.3.3. Biochemical conversion pathway

3.3.3.1. Pretreatment – Only 2G. Pretreatment is a very essential step to support the breakdown of lignin and reduce the crystallinity of cellulose, which is needed for the subsequent breakdown of cellulose and hemicellulose or the increased efficiency of post- pretreatment techniques (Table 12). Many types of pretreatments in physical, chemical, and biochemical categories are used. For sorghum biomass, alkali pretreatment using NaOH was found to be the superior pretreatment method,

Table 11. Comparison of studies using Hydrothermal Liquefaction

Feedstock	Pretreatment	Method points	End Product	Yield/ Observation	Limitation	Reference
Lignocellulosic biomass, algae, wet biomass	Size reduction, slurry preparation	HTL followed by upgrading	Biocrude-derived hydrocarbons	Lowest average price among other pathways- 4 gallon-gasoline equivalent, lowest feedstock cost contribution – 19%	Minimum product selling 4 gallon-gasoline equivalent, lowest feedstock cost contribution – 19%	(17)
Microalgae and macroalgae	Dewatering	HTL with its catalytic variants	Biocrude oil	High energy return on investment compared with other thermochemical routes.	High operating pressure and temperature. High catalyst cost, low stability, Complex fuel upgrading	(23), (24)

due to its delignibility, low energy and cost-effectiveness. Overall, this technique uses huge amounts of energy due to the need for delignification and there is a generation of enzyme inhibitors which hampers the post-pretreatment conversion techniques, especially those involving microbial fermentation (6), (18), (20), (21).

Table 12. Effectiveness of pretreatment on grass biomass vs Woody biomass

Aspect	Grass Biomass	Woody Biomass	References
Primary lignin type	Low lignin content	High Lignin content	(19), (21)
Alkali delignification efficiency	High	Moderate-Low	(20)
Cellulose accessibility post treatment	Higher improvement, accounted to lignin swelling and hemicellulose removal	Weaker improvement, as cellulose is still covered	(16)
Sugar yield improvement	Higher increase in enzymatic hydrolysis yield	Increase less visible, factoring enzyme inhibition	(15), (19)
Overall suitability	High	Low	(19), (20)

3.3.3.2. Enzymatic Hydrolysis – Only 2G. This process is crucial for the conversion of cellulose and hemicellulose in 2nd generation feedstocks into fermentable sugars, that can be fermented with suitable pretreatment. Enzymatic hydrolysis provides a more effective, effective and environmentally friendly method for saccharification than other non-enzyme ones, since enzymes like cellulase, xylanase, etc. help in effective sugar extraction from the biomass . As seen in Table 13, it limits large- scale economic viability due to the related high enzyme costs, sensitivity to pre-treatment derived inhibitors and reduced performance at high loads of biomass. (6), (18), (21)

3.3.3.3. Anaerobic Digestion (Table 14). In this process, biomass of high-water content biomass is converted into biogas like CO₂, ammonia, H₂S and small amounts of hydrogen as well. Biomass that is pre-treated and untreated can be used to produce biogas which can be directly used. Here, the organic matter dissolves into soluble sugar which then get fermented to produce CH₄ and CO₂ which is done with the help of bacteria. Co-digestion, a variation, involves the introduction of carbon rich medium in the form of waste-water streams etc. This helps not only in the proper efficacy of Anaerobic Digestion by increasing C/N ratio in biomass but also helps treat waste-water as well (36).

Anaerobic digestion of lignocellulosic biomass cannot be directly carried out due to lignin’s inhibiting behavior, but is easily overcome by using pretreatment methods mentioned above, which have been proven to increase yields of biofuel . Biomass having high cellulose and hemicellulose content can be effectively and easily processed by this method. Using lignocellulosic biomass, we obtain biogas which consists of CH₄ and CO₂, which is a renewable biofuel and is sustainable since we are valorizing residues that would have been otherwise waste and had drastic impact on the environment. It was found that the ethanol production, from biomass that had been digested, was enhanced which increased the amount of energy or fuel recovered. This was proven in a process simulation study (17), (20), (22), (24), (28).

Table 13. Findings and Limitations of different studies using Enzymatic Hydrolysis as a conversion method.

Feedstock	Findings	Limitation	Reference
Lignocellulosic residues	It has a limit in lignocellulosic ethanol conversion due to sensitivity to enzyme land solid loading, inhibitors and mixing conditions	High enzyme cost, reduced yields at high solids, inhibition by lignin-derived compounds	(21)
Sweet sorghum residue	High sugar release under optimized enzyme dosage at 45-50 deg C and 4.5-5 pH. Depolymerization was confirmed using tests.	Requires effective alkali pretreatment, process sensitive to crystallinity and lignin removal	(6)
General Lignocellulosic biomass	It is preferred over acid hydrolysis due to milder conditions, minimum corrosion and absence of products that degrade sugar.	High enzyme cost, dependency on pretreatment efficiency, inhibitor generation affects hydrolysis	(18)
Wheat straw and other lignocellulosic biomass	Yields 74- 99.6% of max sugar yield (theoretical) on pretreatment	Pretreatment is the most costly and complex step, detoxification often required	(18)
Rice husk	Simultaneous Saccharification and Fermentation (SSF) reduces time compared to Separate hydrolysis and fermentation (SHF).	Trade-off between optimal hydrolysis and fermentation conditions; enzyme inhibition by ethanol in SSF	(12)
Lignocellulosic Biomass waste	Need for High cellulase and Xylanase activity, since enzyme efficiency is proportional to hydrolysis yield.	Enzyme instability, high production cost, and inhibitor sensitivity remain barriers	(30)
Agricultural residues	Confirms effectiveness is due to lignin disruption and cellulose accessibility.	Hybrid pretreatments raise complexity and cost, inhibitors may still form	(20)

Table 14. Insights of different studies using Anaerobic Digestion as a conversion method.

Aspect	Key insight (not already written in text)	Why this matters for biofuel systems	References
Primary role in biorefineries	Functions mainly as a secondary energy recovery and residue management pathway	Prevents misclassification of AD as a primary fuel route	(24)
Unsuitable biomass fractions	Lignin remains largely unconverted under anaerobic conditions	Justifies diversion of lignin to thermochemical pathways	(20)
Energy recovery form	Energy recovered mainly as biogas for heat and electricity, not liquid fuels	Clarifies AD's role in the overall energy mix	(33)
Protein-rich biomass limitation	Excess nitrogen leads to ammonia inhibition of methanogens	Critical for microalgae and some residues	(22)
Need for co-digestion	Single-feedstock digestion often unstable; co-digestion improves buffering	Explains why mono-digestion results vary widely	(36)
Integration advantage	Enables nutrient recycling to cultivation systems	Especially important for algae-based biorefineries	(22)
Scale suitability	Better suited to small-to-medium-scale, decentralized systems	Supports rural and distributed bioenergy models	(15)

3.3.3.4. Bio photolysis – Only 3G. In direct bio photolysis, the microalgae obtain energy from light and splits water in order to obtain hydrogen. In indirect bio photolysis, the organic compounds act as the energy source needed for the splitting. This system can be further improved when the algae is in the absence of oxygen which activate the hydrogen-producing enzyme. A 2-step process was introduced to effectively handle this inhibition due to oxygen. In the 1st stage, algae undergo photosynthesis in the presence of oxygen, which helps in the intake of CO₂ and removal of O₂. Then the algae are introduced to anaerobic condition where hydrogen can be effectively produced^{(22), (24), (27), (28)}. As seen in Table 15, it is a technologically constrained pathway, also limited by the use of an O₂ sensitive enzyme that limits sustained supply of H₂. Breakthroughs in enzyme engineering, reactor efficiency and improved working and oxygen management are needed to access its potential.

Table 15. Comparison of studies using Bio photolysis as conversion technique

Feedstock	Pretreatment and Method	Yield/ Observation	Limitation	Ref-er-ence
Microalgae (Chlamydomonas Chlorella)	Anaerobic induction, nutrient deprivation, inert gas purging, Direct photolysis	Transient H ₂ production, improved yields under O ₂ removal strategies	High O ₂ sensitivity of hydrogenase, poor scalability, small production duration	(28)
Microalgae	Mechanical, Direct and Indirect bio photolysis	Feasibility under controlled conditions	Low Productivity, high light demand, inefficient reactor	(32)
Algal Biomass	Bio photolysis	Clean H ₂ route	Lack of Technology, Oxygen inhibition, economic problems	(22)
Algae	Bio photolysis	Conceptual feasibility	Low yields, Lack of Technology	(28)

4 Discussion

4.1 Techno-economic Aspect

4.1.1. Cost structure and drivers

In 2nd generation biofuel pathways, techno-economic feasibility is achieved by processing cost rather than feedstock cultivation. As seen in Table 16, studies show that pretreatment and enzymatic hydrolysis greatly affect total production cost due to the energy intensity of pretreatments and high loading requirement of commercial cellulolytic enzymes. Process simulation show that decreasing pretreatment severity leads to increased enzyme demands or longer residence times. This limits isolation and cost reduction of the concerns to decrease total costs.

From Table 17, we see that in 3rd generation biofuel pathways, cultivation, harvesting and dewatering primarily increase operational expenses. They are capital intensive usually when Photobioreactors are used. These costs cannot be reduced by single stage optimization but need changes in the pathway itself.

4.1.2. Process optimization and scalability

In 2nd generation biofuel pathways are performed at pilot- to demonstration scales which use existing agricultural supply chains and well- established fermentation technologies. However as seen in Table 16, high capital investment and complex operation, particularly in pretreatment and separation, hinders large scale deployment.

In contrast, 3rd generation pathways are confined to laboratory and pilot scales. Table 17 shows that despite technical feasibility, large scale biofuels production is economically inconsistent due to challenges like cultivation, harvesting and processing. This tells us that scalability rather than yield potential is responsible for these pathways being techno-economically unfeasible.

4.1.3. Yield vs. Cost paradox

For 2nd generation feedstocks, increase in sugar release or ethanol yield is faced by high energy consumption, chemical and enzyme use, which results in negative cost benefits. Hence, we see in Table 16, that yield optimization alone does not increase economic feasibility unless there are parallel reductions in energy and capital.

This paradox is even more obvious for the 3rd generation, as in Table 17, Cultivation and harvesting is energy intensive which nullifies the biological advantages of microalgae. The finding demonstrate that this advantage alone is not enough to guarantee techno-economic feasibility.

4.1.4. Energy-normalized performance indicators

To combat the limitation of yield- based metrics, energy- normalized indicators give a more meaningful parameter for techno-economic comparison. Energy conversion efficiency and net energy balance easily helps us find the energy invested and recovered. As seen in Table 18, assessments of sweet sorghum bagasse ethanol, shows us that favorable ethanol yields do not correspond to net energy gains when we consider pretreatment and distillation of energy inputs.

Process-level simulations confirm that feedstocks with moderate yield but lower energy requirements can outperform high yield systems in the 3rd generation feedstock pathways.

Despite the high relevance of these indicators, they remain underutilized in comparative techno-economic studies.

4.1.5. Role of co-products and integrated biorefineries

Integration of co-product streams seen in integrated biorefineries are very effective strategies. Integrated lignocellulosic biorefineries improve economic feasibility by valorizing lignin and other by-products compared to single-product systems.

In 3rd generation pathways, in Table 17, we see that this co-product system can substantially reduce the minimum selling price of algal biofuels. Advancement of these systems ensure that capital and operation costs are spread across many products.

4.1.6. Real world deployments

Recent initiatives in Malaysia and Japan demonstrate the technical feasibility of continuous microalgae cultivation but as seen in Table 17, there are challenges like cost, energy demand and infrastructure requirements. Pilot scale algal biorefineries that operate under variable climate demonstrates the sensitivity of production costs to the site-specific factors. These sites, show us how renewable energy integration, co-product valorization and optimization of the site improves economic viability.

Table 16. Techno- economic analysis in 2nd generation biofuel pathways

Feedstock	Scale/ Method	Cost Contributors	Energy integration	Techno-economic info
Mixed Lignocellulosic residues	Techno-economic review	Pretreatment and enzymatic hydrolysis account for more than 25-30% of total production cost, depending on configuration	Cogeneration helps in mitigating cost due to energy needs	Conversion greatly affects total costs compared to overall costs.
Wheat straw, miscanthus, eucalyptus, spruce	Process simulation	Pretreatment- associated sugar losses and energy demand reduce efficiency	Energy- autonomous operation of combusting lignin using Combined heat and power unit.	Composition of feedstocks affects efficiency more than yield
Sweet sorghum bagasse	Pilot-scale energy assessment	Pretreatment and distillation take huge amount of energy	Positive net energy balance at favorable conditions	High ethanol yield does not guarantee good energy balance
Mixed lignocellulosic feedstocks	Industrial outlook	Enzymes, detoxification and pretreatment	Qualitative	Conversion complexity is stopping deployment in commercial setting

Table 17. Techno- economic analysis in 3rd generation biofuel pathways

Cultivation system	Scale/ Method	Cost Info	Cost contributors	Co- product use
Open pond systems	Pilot	Biofuel production cost is much higher than fossil fuels	Harvesting, dewatering. Energy demand	Not included
Mixed algal systems	Review	Cost of algal biofuels easily varies due to current technologies	Energy demand and high capital	Partially discussed
Photobioreactors and open pond systems	Pilot/ demo	High minimum selling price, highly depends on system design	Photo bioreactors, cultivation energy	Emerging in biorefineries
Integrated algal biorefinery	Techno-economic model	Substantial reduction in fuels' minimum selling price in co-production	Cost reduced by valorization	Essential for being economically feasible

4.2 Environmental Aspect

4.2.1. Second- generation Biofuels- GHG mitigation

These systems that are cultivated on marginal or degraded land have shown to achieve net GHG reduction relative to fossil fuels, using soil carbon sequestration and low nitrogen fertilizer requirements. Perennial grasses like Miscanthus and switchgrass are able to perform the above and benefit from its long life and minimal agricultural inputs. As seen in Table 19, these advantages

Table 18. Energy performance indicators and analysis

Feedstock and system	Indicator	Observation	Interpretation
Organic waste- Co-digestion	Energy conversion efficiency (ECE)	ECE was defined and optimized	Normalization of energy metrics enable comparison
Sweet sorghum bagasse- ethanol pathway	Net energy Balance (NEB)	Positive but depends on pretreatment and distillation energy	Sustainability cannot be achieved with yield itself
Multiple lignocellulosic feedstocks	Energy efficiency	27-46% depending feedstock used	Moderate yield systems outperform those with high yields
Microalgae- biorefinery	Energy intensity	High energy demands	Energy input needs limit economic feasibility

are applicable only when land-use change is avoided and residue management practices are optimized. However, large scale expansion can induce land use change, disruption of ecosystem and increase fertilizer demand, nullifying the GHG savings. Therefore, these biofuels are environmentally favorable only when land-use is observed.

4.2.2. Third- generation Biofuels- Energy- Source sensitivity

Algal cultivation can be conducted in non, arable land, saline and wastewater streams, therefore reducing competition with food and freshwater resources. However, life cycle assessments reveal that environmental performance is constrained by cultivation, harvesting and dewatering. As seen in Table 20, Photobioreactors powered by fossil – derived electricity exhibits neutral or net positive GHG emission due to high energy demand by mixing, aeration and temperature control. In contrast, incorporation of renewable electricity or waste heat improves effect on environment, indicating that energy source decarbonization is an obvious requirement for net GHG reduction.

4.2.3. Resource- use trade- offs and environmental burden shifting

While 2nd generation systems benefit from marginal land use, they remain vulnerable to land- use change and biodiversity loss if deployed at large scale. In contrast, microalgal systems minimize land-use but introduce risks related to nutrient leakage, eutrophication and water loss, usually in open-pond conditions.

From Table 21, we can see that environment burdens are usually shifter, rather than reducing only a single concern. For example, reduction in land-use is accompanied by high energy demand and avoiding fertilizer leads to increased electrical consumption.

4.2.4. Integrated pathways and environmental- economic coupling

Integrated biorefineries provide a pathway to mitigate environmental effects, using waste valorization and resource recovery. Studies show that combining microalgal cultivation with wastewater treatment or having co-product recovery in lignocellulosic biorefineries can reduce overall environmental burdens considerably while increasing economic feasibility. Environmental stability and techno-economic feasibility cannot be considered separately but are dependent on one another. This emphasizes the need for combined assessments, rather than separate ones.

Table 19. Life cycle Greenhouse Gas (GHG) performance for 2nd generation biofuel pathways

Feedstock/ System	Cultivation info	GHG Trends	Contributors
Miscanthus, Switchgrass	Marginal/ degraded land	Net GHG reduction relative to fossil fuels	Soil carbon sequestration, low Nitrogen input
Sweet sorghum residues	Agricultural residues	Moderate GHG reduction	Avoiding residue combustion, fermentation efficiency
Lignocellulosic crops	Land expansion scenarios	Neutral to negative GHG	Indirect land- use change, fertilizer use

5 Conclusion

This review shows that second-generation biofuel feedstocks offer high waste recovery and CO2 sequestration but limited due to complex pretreatment processes, enzymatic hydrolysis and limited commercial scalability. Third-generation algal feedstocks

Table 20. Environmental performance analysis of 3rd generation biofuel pathways

System	Energy source	GHG Trends	Limitation
Photobioreactors	Fossil fuels	Neutral to net positive emissions	High electricity demand for mixing and aeration
Photobioreactors	Renewable electricity	Net GHG reduction	Energy decarbonization
Open pond	Mixed grid electricity	Depends on site	Evaporation, nutrient losses

Table 21. Resource use tradeoffs and environmental analysis of 2nd and 3rd generation biofuel pathways

System type	Resource use	Environmental info	Changes made
Second- generation crop- systems	Marginal land use	Ecosystem disturbance	Land- use change offsets GHG emissions
Microalgae- open ponds	Non arable land, saline and waste water	Eutrophication risk	Nutrient leakage, water loss
Integrated biorefineries	Waste (for valorization)	System Complexity reduces environmental harm	Emissions shifted to energy supply

show high photosynthetic energy efficiency, reduce land competition and water pollution, but their commercialization is limited by its costly cultivation and high energy consuming harvesting techniques. We found that in the various conversion technologies, pretreatment and enzymatic hydrolysis for second-generation and bio photolysis for third generation are bottlenecks faced by the respective feedstocks. There is great potential in hybrid biorefineries, where lignocellulosic biomass is combined with algal systems which will increase yield, energy productivity and help reduce greenhouse gas emissions but its use is restricted by technology and financial issues. Future research should be done for improving pretreatment technologies, hybrid biorefinery models, and valorization of all waste and byproducts to make biofuels more favorable and commercially acceptable.

The review clearly shows a mismatch between the two generations of feedstocks and their roles in biomass and bioenergy production. On one hand, second generation biofuels are derived from lignocellulosic feedstocks, whereas, on the other hand, third generation biofuels are derived from algal biomass.

From second generation biofuel perspective, the feedstocks show high sustainability, waste valorization, decreased competitiveness, and mitigate greenhouse gas emissions by soil carbon sequestration. A major factor is energy recovery and carbon performance, which accounts for reducing the energy penalty and comparing biofuels to traditional fossil fuels by their carbon dioxide emissions during either fuel production or usage. These procedures increase operating costs and limit usage of biofuels due to inhibitor formation. This leads to yield-cost and yield-energy paradox.

From third generation biofuel perspective, its strengths are a high growth and photosynthesis rate. Some advantages of third generation compared to the second generation are land use flexibility, wastewater utilization and carbon dioxide capturing potential. This is visible in integrated biorefinery and renewable energy coupled systems. The limitations arise in terms of techno-economic analysis, where there is a lot of wasted energy.

The limitation in the chemical pathway for energy production has been deactivation of catalysts. This causes waste of solid fuels like wood. A possible solution is adding additives like boron to the catalyst, aiding trapping poisons, namely Sulfur and Phosphorus. In third generation, algae, to date, has not been able to provide energy due to limited sunlight as energy for them to grow. The possible solution is making Hydrogen-Carbon yield more efficient and increasing lipid content. Processes like Biochar synergy, to lower energy for water splitting to avoid waste production.

Unlike previous reviews that have only focused on either one, second or third generation, biofuels separately, this review states both generations together and showcases them with the help of a comparative study. It considers constraints like scalability, performance, and conversion technologies that help find bottlenecks in the previous paper studies conducted to improve energy efficiency and reduce greenhouse gas emissions.

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